

Welcome to the May newsletter, lots of news, resources and events to share starting with an exciting funding opportunity for you. Enjoy!

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Metascience funding opportunity with fellow LNLs

STOP PRESS: The UKRI have launched a UK metascience research grants scheme. More information [here](#). If you are interested in developing an application for this call with fellow LNLs please contact LNL David Smailes

and/or attend an extraordinary GatherTown meet-up at 9.30 on Monday 13th May - [link here](#)

Queen's University Belfast LNLs PhD student Bethan Iley and lecturer Dr Joost Dessing

Spotlight on open research at Queen's University Belfast

Our recent [blog](#) spotlights open research activities at Queen's University, Belfast and the work of Joost Dessing and Bethan Iley. Learn why Joost committed to doing open research, how LNLs inspire their students, the Queen's Open Science Work Group and their local network activities.

Joost would like to hear from you. As part of REF2029 preparation, Joost's department are discussing guidance for internal reviewers of submission papers, including making them aware of how open research impacts research paper quality. What criteria should be included? Should Registered Reports be given a higher ranking? Joost would be interested to know how other departments are tackling this challenge and suggests this could be a discussion topic for the LNL community. Please feel free to contact Joost to discuss.

Previous LNL workshops - now resources for you

Workshop 4: Understanding the workings of an institution

In an entertaining and informative presentation [now available on](#)

[Youtube](#), Etienne Roesch shared his experience of the practical steps needed to reach the right people in the right way and how he used this understanding to develop policies within his institution. The talk follows on nicely from his previous workshop 'Mentorship: you and your community' available [here](#). Another useful resource is Robert Darby's primer: [Checklist for an Open Research Action Plan](#). Etienne also discussed the importance of followers using a Youtube video where a 'dancing shirtless guy' starts a movement. Intrigued? Then watch Etienne's talk [here](#)

Workshop 2: Building the LNL – Open Research Enabler relationship

This workshop brought together LNLs and open research enablers, including ORCAs (Open Research Coordinators & Administrators based at institutes involved in the UKRN Open Research Programme) to learn more about communications within their institute so they can be more effective in their respective roles. A recording of the presentations is [here](#).

Workshop 1: Setting up a student consortium for undergraduate final year projects

A recording of the presentation by Kait Clark (LNL University of the West of England - UWE) is now [available](#). If anyone would like to be included in a future student consortium please contact Kait.

Upcoming LNL workshops

Workshop 5: Mindset awareness

This will be presented by Nikki Osborne, Director of [Responsible Research in Practice](#). An awareness of how mindset can impact research culture can help discussions on how to support change. The workshop will enable LNLs to work together on activities to understand more about fixed and growth mindsets, and to reflect on how these mindsets affect themselves and others

13 June 13:00pm – 14:00pm Register [here](#)

Workshop 6: Writing Retreat

We are running another all day writing retreat - it's an opportunity for some light social activity, as well as carving out a solid block of time to dedicate to writing/coding/analysis. Set your out-of-office and devote maximum headspace to your task. The day will be led by Sarah Gunn, LNL University of Leicester.

(Wednesday) 10 July 9:30 – 16:00 (optional later finish at 17:30) Register [here](#)

December workshop: Replication games – all day event

It's a long way off but we're so excited we wanted to share the details with you. This will be an all-day event run by Abel Brodeur from the [Institute for Replication](#). Consider it an early Christmas present from us to you. More details to follow

5 December 9:30 – 17:30 Register [here](#)

Would YOU like to run a workshop? We still have a few slots left. Get in touch contact@ukrn.org

Other UKRN resources

[Exploring Research Transparency, Positionality and Reproducibility](#)

The recent UKRN webinar on '**Reproducibility, Transparency and Positionality? Perspectives from different research fields**' coincided with the publication of the UKRN Working Paper '[Exploring Research Transparency, Positionality and Reproducibility](#)' in collaboration with the British Psychological Society and the Practice as Research Advisory Group UK (PRAG-UK). The UKRN webinar is available on the UKRN YouTube channel [here](#)

The March 2024 UKRN webinar '**Indicators for Open Research: Pilot Projects**' was very well attended and has been popular on Youtube. You can watch it [here](#).

Upcoming UKRN webinars

Introduction to power analysis via simulation in R

**Insect Welfare
Research Society**

**Online workshop
16th May 2024**

Introduction to power analysis via simulation in R

May 16 13:00 - 15:00

The goal of this webinar is to provide a functional introduction to performing power analyses via simulation. Power analyses are vital tools that can provide an estimate of sample sizes required for a given experiment. Participants will be guided through the code needed to run their own simulations and are encouraged to bring their own experiment plans for live, interactive analysis. Register [here](#).

UKRN: A Space Odyssey (a journey through the STAR and METEOR projects)

June 20, 2024 13:00 - 15:00

Learn more about these two UKRN projects, co-funded by UKRN members. STAR (Sustainable and TrAnsparent Research data) reviews the arrangements institutions have in place to support open data. METEOR (METa-research for the Enhancement of Research culture) explores how institutions use research evidence to inform their research culture. This webinar will present preliminary findings and emerging themes from both projects. Followed by Q&A session. Register [here](#)

Speakers:

Jess Wheeler: Senior Research Associate in Qualitative Research, Project Lead for STAR

Pen-Yuan Hsing: Senior Research Associate, STAR project

Robbie Clark: Research Associate, METEOR project

Ros Strang: Project Coordinator, STAR and METEOR projects

Other events

[Open Publishing Fest - online event](#)

June 3 - 14, 2024

A public event from the [Coko Foundation](#) that brings together communities supporting open source software, open content, and open publishing models. Find out more [here](#). For more information or to discuss ideas, please email adam@coko.foundation

Reading recommendations

[Researchers need 'open' bibliographic databases](#)

A recent comment piece by Catherine Offord in Science highlights the [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#). Signatories to the declaration commit to: making openness the default for research information they use and produce, working to support and enable open research information, supporting the sustainability of infrastructures and collective action to accelerate the transition to openness of research information. Read more about the declaration [here](#).

With thanks to Marcus Munafò for sharing this paper.

[Understanding the provenance and quality of methods is essential for responsible reuse of FAIR data](#)

As many of you will know, FAIR data is findable, accessible, interoperable and

reusable. However, the authors of this Correspondence, recently published in Nature Medicine by Tracey Weissgerber and colleagues, note that 'open data are not necessarily FAIR, and FAIR data are not necessarily open'. They propose the creation of guiding principles to 'facilitate and enhance responsible data reuse'.

With thanks to Emma Ganley from [FAIRsharing](#) - a curated resource on data and metadata standards, inter-related to databases and data policies - for sharing this paper.

[Open access journal publication in health and medical research and open science: benefits, challenges and limitations](#)

As the title suggest, this paper by Patricia Logullo and colleagues discusses the benefits, challenges and limitations of open access publications.

[X-Net Recommendations Report on Interdisciplinary Research](#)

[X-Net](#) is a training network at the interface between computational and mathematical sciences and biomedical research. It is funded by MRC and managed and supported by the Universities of Dundee, Edinburgh and Oxford. The X-Net recommendations report was released in March 2024 and aims to 'sweep away barriers to interdisciplinary research' and 'highlight common career and funding barriers'. The report also offers recommendations to increase the retention and impact of interdisciplinary researchers in the UK. Read more [here](#).

Share your resources

If you've read a great paper that you want to share with your fellow LNLs let us know and we can share it contact@ukrn.org